

FAGUS BAUHOLZ

Swiss made high strength structural timber

Beech hardwood lamellas are processed into high performance glued laminated timber providing constructive elements for high mechanical load applications such as wide span roofs and multi-storey buildings.

Highlights of innovative features

- Beech wood is abundant in Swiss forests, but so far it is poorly valorized and large volumes end up directly in bioenergy use. This product converts such raw material instead into a high-end use.
- FAGUS structural timber has 2x higher bending and tensile strength and 3x higher compression and shear strength compared to conventional softwood glulam.
- It enables extended spans and slender construction elements with less timber volume. The single beam maximal dimensions are 0.28 x 1.24 x 13.5m.
- It replaces energy intensive products such as steel and concrete and provides long-term carbon storage in buildings.
- Production rejects are used for manufacturing of solid wood furniture panels and other products.

Swiss Confederation
Innosuisse – Swiss Innovation Agency

For architects and planners, the high-performance beech wood is a pioneer building product, because it allows for more filigree designs offering new aesthetic and constructive possibilities.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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